
Deliverable D1.3.2 SOPs for specific WGS proficiency testing distributions

Workpackage 1, 1.3.2.

Responsible Partner: APHA, SSI

Contributing partners: DTU, SSI, UCM,
PIWET, APHA, ISS, RIVM, WBVR, SLV, FOHM,
SVA, ANSES

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

JIP/JRP deliverable	D 1.3.2 SOPs for specific WGS proficiency testing distributions		
Project Acronym	CARE		
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Due month of the report	58		
Actual submission month	60		
Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R Save date: December 16, 2022		
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU		
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 2 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 3 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	OHEJP WP 4 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 5 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 6 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	OHEJP WP 7 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
	Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Scientific Steering Board <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
	National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
	EFSA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	ECDC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
	Other	international	stakeholder(s):
		
	Social Media:		
	Other recipient(s):		

1. Summary

The development of new Proficiency Tests (PT) / External Quality Assessments (EQA) are necessary to support the implementation of novel diagnostics technologies such as Whole Genome Sequencing (WGS) and have great value assisting cross-sectoral partnerships focusing on One Health approaches; this is high on the agenda for infectious disease control.

Proficiency testing (PT) and External Quality Assessments (EQA) involves the use of inter-laboratory comparisons (by two or more laboratories) for the assessment of laboratory performance. The need for ongoing confidence in laboratory performance is not only essential for laboratories and their stakeholders, but also for other interested parties such as regulators and accreditation bodies.

PT/EQA organisers must ensure the schemes are fit for purpose for the participants and their testing methodologies. They should suitably challenge a laboratory's performance capabilities, diagnostics assays and test methods (particularly diagnostic specificity and sensitivity) and so prove its usefulness in the laboratory. Well designed and executed PT/EQA programmes enable participants to monitor and identify trends and gaps in their diagnostic performances, so that corrective actions, preventative actions and improvements can be implemented.

Accredited PT/EQA providers operate in accordance with ISO/IEC 17043 (Conformity Assessment – General Requirements for proficiency testing).

This standard covers aspects required for the successful operation of PT/EQA exercises, including but not limited to:

- Planning and design
- Operation
- Management
- Personnel
- Confidentiality
- Assuring Quality e.g., supply of material
- Data analysis and evaluation of results

The design, planning and operation of any PT/EQA should be documented by the provider.

A proven template (and accompanying guidance document) was adapted and used for the three pilot WGS PT/EQA exercises organised in WP1. This template addresses the criteria for setting up and running PT/EQA's as noted in ISO/IEC 17043.

2. PT/EQA for Whole genome Sequencing

Whole genome sequencing (WGS) techniques are growing in popularity. The importance of developing PTs to assess and monitor this technology is significant for disease outbreak investigations, surveillance, and research purposes.

PT/EQA schemes consist of a single sample or several PT samples. A predefined outcome should be applied to the sample results. These are usually determined either as a consensus of participants results or have 'known' measurands or characteristics for example, certified reference material,

quality control material, DNA and simulated or real specimens that have fully characterised sequencing data incl cluster outbreak analysis data.

PT/EQA's for such technology are in a state of infancy and consequently the variety of analytical methodologies deems it impossible at this stage, to allocate a predefined outcome to the PT sample results, based on the consensus results from participating laboratories. PT/EQA samples for WGS should be prepared from reference materials or from material with a 'known' value. For *in silico* analysis, samples can be rerun applying different analytical approaches, however the PT provider needs the resources to do so; and some computer tools require a licence.

There are three distinct components within a WGS testing process and these are divided into the following: -

- Wet lab processes – assess the laboratories ability to perform DNA preparation and sequencing procedures.
- Dry processes - In *silico* analysis of DNA data to assess e.g. the differences among laboratories in the detection of variants (single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) from the analysis of whole genome sequence data. An IT system/platform e.g. FTP (File Transfer Protocol) site is required to facilitate the upload and download of data. Each stage can be assessed independently using PT but the whole testing process must function correctly to provide a valid result.

If the PT/EQA scheme consists of PT samples containing live strains, they must be verified that they are stable for the duration of the PT exercise period. Files with DNA information are more stable.

Following testing, the participants should report the results to the PT provider within a specific time frame.

Statistical analyses may be performed on the results according to in house documented procedures; these may be based on ISO 13528 - Statistical methods for use in proficiency testing by interlaboratory comparison (ISO 13528 supports ISO/IEC 17043).

The PT/EQA results, once submitted by the participants, are assessed by a technical expert; commentary is usually provided. This often includes:

- Overall performance versus prior expectations, taking uncertainties into account
- Variation within and between laboratories (and comparisons with any previous schemes or published precision data)
- Variation between methods, assays or procedures
- Possible sources of error (noting extreme results) and suggestions for improving performance
- Advice and educational feedback to participants to aid continual improvement
- Situations where unusual factors make evaluation of results and commentary on performance impossible.
- Any other suggestions, recommendations, general comments and encourage feedback
- Conclusions

The full reports including participants, results, statistical calculations and comments on performance must be checked and authorised prior to issue.

The identity of participants and all other information relating to participants, in most cases, remain confidential; exceptions might where PT/EQA exercises are organised by public laboratories.

The development and implementation of a new PT/EQA must be documented.

A template for the design, planning, execution and evaluation of cross sectoral PT/EQA's (Appendix 1) was used for the operation of the pilot PT schemes. An accompanying document for guidance on how to complete the template is available (Appendix 2).

The template was used for setting up and running the pilot WGS PT/EQA exercises completed within work package 1. Two examples of the completed template are available:

- Pilot PT on isolation/detection and characterization of pathogens (Appendix 3)
- Pilot PT on outbreak surveillance based on WGS data (Appendix 4)

Once a PT/EQA has been designed, a subsequent pilot PT exercise is run, usually with a small number of participants.

Feedback should always be encouraged from laboratories participating in a pilot distribution, so improvements or changes can be made prior to the PT/EQA being offered more widely.

3. Conclusion

The operation of PT/EQA exercises for WGS is an evolving process. From a One Health perspective, the focus should be to continue to develop PT/EQA exercises and collate and share information and metadata. This will aid the improvement and standardisation of 'wet' laboratory and bioinformatics analyses so that laboratories within all sectors can achieve comparable characterisation of isolates (Johnson et al 2021).

The template has proved to be a useful tool in the set-up of a PT/EQA scheme acting as a comprehensive checklist, capturing the requirements as laid out in ISO/IEC 17043. The components covered are detailed in the guidance document (Appendix 2). It can be adapted to suit (as seen in appendix 3 and 4) and offers the PT/EQA provider a good start to help design and operate a robust PT/EQA programme suitable for use across single and multiple sectors.

In this case, feedback about the template and guidance document was gratefully received from colleagues across the CARE 'One Health' EJP sectors in WP1.

4. References

Johnson P. Cabuang L. (2021). Proficiency testing and Ring Trials: World Organisation for Animal Health, Diagnostic test validation science Scientific and Technical Review, Vol. 40 (1), 2021

Appendix 1

Template for the design, planning, execution and evaluation of cross sectoral PTs

NEW PT SCHEME – PLANNING AND DESIGN

SCHEME PLAN

Scheme Title:		PT Scheme number	
Introduction and purpose of scheme			
What are the challenges for participants, other than finding the target analyte, does the scheme offer? e.g. dilutions of the same sample, duplicate samples, negatives, sera with antibodies to other diseases			
Determinands:			
Test method(s):			

TECHNICAL EXPERTS CONSULTED

Technical expert involved at scheme planning (name) – test / disease expert, statistician, other. Give reason for using this expert.	

WGS PTs STRAIN SELECTION

- Strain selection inclusive of different sectors e.g vet, human, food

SAMPLE DETAILS

Number of samples per distribution	
Sample volume	
Where raw material is obtained, what is the source / origin	
Samples produced In-house or external provider	
Details of how samples are produced:	
Primary test method used to verify the sample / bulk stock / product	
Details of how/where samples are dispatched from. If dispatched externally, how has the dispatcher been assessed and deemed acceptable	
Where samples/material have been subjected to any inactivation procedure how is it known that this has not ruined the product	
Where appropriate have the samples / material been checked to ensure the disease causing agent is non viable? Is the inactivation process validated?	
Homogeneity (section 4.4.3 ISO/IEC 17043) Method used to ensure homogeneity (where applicable) Criteria used to define acceptability of the test results for homogeneity eg no of samples tested that should all give the	

NEW PT SCHEME – PLANNING AND DESIGN

sample interpretation of the result – or where enumeration is used is there a range of where the results should lie. Give details of Method used to ensure homogeneity where applicable	
What effect would non – homogeneous samples or batch of samples have on the intended result or the participants results	
Stability (section 4.4.3 ISO/IEC 17043) Expiry of samples or shelf life applied. How stability has been assessed. Consider how instability would affect participants results	
Record metrological traceability of samples: e.g. reference strains (may not always be possible for all samples)	
Criteria used to define acceptability of intended result	
Information to be included on intended result for final report	
Is sample availability limited e.g scarce	
Any potential major sources of error	
Establish the criteria for uncertainty	

	Handling requirements	Storage requirements
Raw material		
Samples in final form		
On receipt by lab		
Details of Safety aspects issued (to be completed by sample production department):		

SUPPLIERS OF MATERIAL & SAMPLES

Source for supply of samples or material for samples (name, location & details) YES / NO		
Give details of samples/material supplier's status ie quality status or other reason they are approved as a supplier Incl details for both positive and negative samples.		

WGS DATA COLLECTION

Which platforms were used for the analysis of the WGS sequences	
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SUB CONTRACTORS - TESTING OF SAMPLES

	Test 1	Test 2	Test 3
Record test method(s) details			

NEW PT SCHEME – PLANNING AND DESIGN

Lab(s) used for checking / validation of samples or raw material (name, location & details)			
Are they ISO17025 accredited for the relevant test			
Are they ISO17025 accredited other similar test but not the relevant test			
Are they certified to ISO 9001			
Do they hold a status of national/ international ref centre or known centre of excellence/quality			
Are they a long term subcontractor/collaborator for PT Provider with a proven track record			
Do they meet other defined requirements eg specialist facilities			
Details of any other assessment or evaluation of testing sub-contractor			
where applicable record the Consensus values – where used indicate why and estimate the uncertainty of the assigned value			
Environmental conditions (section 4.3 ISO/IEC 17043) Give consideration to storage, transportation and subcontractors facilities. Include handling and disposal of hazardous materials.			
Equipment. Suitability and monitoring: State if covered by ISO 17025. If not assess alternative quality system suitability eg – validated method used or are SOP's / protocols implemented or manufacturers instructions used. Are calibration certificates held? Use of reference stds. Note if QC or PT samples are used to check equipment suitability, and confirm method reliability / method validation			
Other comments			

SUBCONTRACTOR – SCHEME COMMENTS

Name and location of Primary, deputy, secondary test commentators (TC) (for provision of evaluation of results)	
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NEW PT SCHEME – PLANNING AND DESIGN

Rationale for selection of TC(s)	
CV / details of experience	
Have TC's been sent confidentiality agreement, guidelines for TC's and details of what appears on the TC report, compared to the final report issued to participants.	

OPERATION OF SCHEME

Sample distribution - postage requirements	
Additional requirements;	
Samples to be issued by (eg Co-ordinator, subcontractor or other dept)	

DOCUMENTATION / PT LIMS

Standard paperwork for labwork file	
Sample request sheet (standard template which may need amending depending on sample type and tests done).	
Stock list produced	
Scheme details entered on computer	
Scheme details	
Sample No. sequence	
Test information – test type, result & method items	
Scheme instructions for labs – ensure these do not impinge on a lab's routine method. Has storage upon receipt been included	
Results tabulation- Results reporting form agreed (Note: no accreditation symbol to be applied initially until PT is awarded accreditation)	

PARTICIPATION

Pilot scheme due	
Likely Number of participants in pilot	
Participant criteria to be met before joining scheme (where applicable)	
Collusion – consider the potential for collusion (incl post distribution to pre disclosure of results and any preventative measures)	

DISTRIBUTION

Fixed Term? YES /NO (if yes enter period)	YES / NO
Time limit from distribution to deadline for results	
Week of issue	
Frequency of issue (e.g. monthly or state months)	

RESULTS REPORTING

Assigned values/intended results – how displayed	
Data reported to participants as (eg electronic tabulated results showing all participants results)	
How performance evaluation techniques are assessed/displayed where appropriate (eg mean of sample results)	

NEW PT SCHEME – PLANNING AND DESIGN

Specific requirements on results reporting to be agreed externally?	
Statistical analysis carried out – yes / no (if yes, by whom)	
Basis of performance evaluation techniques	
Details of result / report to be published	

COSTING

Costing record (filename) Full economic cost (FEC)	
Costing carried out by	

PROCEDURES

	Sample production	Scheme operation	
Nominated author (if in-house)			
SOP number			
SOP title			
Related National SOP reference(s) for test method if known e.g. ISO			

VALIDATION (PT fit for purpose) / VERIFICATION (meets participants requirements)

Pilot Scheme

Distribution Number	
Date of issue	
Participants as distribution list?	
Further pilots required yes / no if yes give details	
Has the feedback form been sent to participants following pilot scheme.	
Did all participants' results match the intended results?	
Were the samples used at an appropriate dilution in terms of the test and for economic reasons (ie. so no wastage of material)	
Is there any further action to be taken?	

SCHEME – FIT FOR PURPOSE

What criteria is used to determine the scheme is fit for purpose	
Does the scheme meet the proposed requirements ?	
Signature / Date	

CONTRACTS

Is scheme now to be offered commercially? Give date if yes	
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NEW PT SCHEME – PLANNING AND DESIGN

Has a PT scheme information sheet been finalised and published on website? Has the PT been added to the price list?	
Signature / Date	

OTHER INFORMATION / COMMENTS RELEVANT TO SCHEME

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RESOURCES

Contract Review - Deliverables established

Criteria	Available	Criteria	Available
Staff	Appropriate number <input type="checkbox"/>	Training <input type="checkbox"/>	
	Provision for staff turnover <input type="checkbox"/>	Experience <input type="checkbox"/>	
	Sufficient supervisors/management <input type="checkbox"/>	Competence <input type="checkbox"/>	
Lab accommodation	Adequate space <input type="checkbox"/>	Adequate storage for samples <input type="checkbox"/>	
	Adequate heating / ventilation <input type="checkbox"/>		
Consumables / materials	Suppliers approved <input type="checkbox"/>	Quantities assessed / deliverable <input type="checkbox"/>	
	Sufficient PT material <input type="checkbox"/>		
Safety	Risk assessed <input type="checkbox"/>	Samples <input type="checkbox"/>	
Equipment / IT	All necessary equipment available <input type="checkbox"/>	Data processing software <input type="checkbox"/>	
Sufficient resources for PT Scheme	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>		No <input type="checkbox"/>
Signed _____	Name		Date

Appendix 2

Guidance document on how to complete the template

Guidance document

Proficiency Testing (PT), External Quality Assessments (EQA) and Ring Trials (RT) are an integral part of laboratory quality assurance. They have numerous diverse uses and appraising a laboratory's PT results over time can illustrate whether a laboratory's performance is stable, improving or worsening. With the focus on the standardisation of methods, PTs also highlight variations in the performance of assays and its educational value should not be underestimated.

The development of new PTs can support the implementation of novel diagnostics technologies such as whole genome sequencing and point-of-care testing and assist in cross-sectoral partnerships focusing on One Health approaches, which are high on the agenda for infectious disease control. More information about this is detailed in CARE One Health EJP Report D.1.1.1 - 'Mapping of existing and proposals for new PT schemes WP1'.

The challenges for PT providers remain significant for example, availability and accessibility of suitable biological and reference materials are essential for a PT provider to execute its duties. Resources must be directed towards increasing and improving the quality of PT and constantly accommodate the new methods that are being applied.

Operation of a PT/EQA/RT scheme involves selecting and verifying suitable panels of samples that are stable and homogeneous. It also includes data capture and analysis, assigning a value to samples and setting criteria for pass and fail. Reassessment of PTs is necessary to ensure they remain fit for purpose.

Once designed, subsequent pilot PT/EQA/RT exercise which is conducted on a small-scale basis with participants must provide evidence that the PT is suitably challenging a laboratory's performance capabilities, diagnostics assays, and test methods (particularly diagnostic specificity and sensitivity) and so prove its usefulness in the laboratory.

The standard to which PT providers must conform to be accredited is ISO/IEC 17043 Conformity assessment – General requirements for proficiency testing.

ISO standard 13528 supports and is complementary to ISO/IEC 17043 for the statistical analysis of PT results.

Note that accreditation is applied to PT programmes rather than the entirety of the PT provider.

The planning and design of a new PT scheme EQA or RT by a PT provider can be carried out using a template that follows the requirements laid out in ISO/IEC 17043. This template 'New PT scheme planning and design document' is a comprehensive checklist capturing all evidence and data for the design and operation of a PT scheme.

The main features in this template are as follows: -

- **Scheme Plan:** - Addresses the objectives, purpose, and basic design of the PT scheme
- **Technical Experts:** - It is necessary to have input from a technical specialist with experience in diagnostic testing relevant to the PT/EQA/RT and if possible, some knowledge of the associated disease, statistical analysis, who can provide comments on technical difficulties, feedback and evaluate results
- **Sample Details /Strain selection/Data collection:** - Sample types (or microbiological strains) should match as closely as practicable, in terms of the matrix, measurands and concentrations, to the test items routinely analysed in laboratories. Participants must receive comparable PT/EQA/RT samples that are homogenous (both within the samples and throughout the batch) and remain stable throughout the duration of the PT period, this requires careful planning, manufacturing & transportation. The criteria for homogeneity and stability shall be established, with consideration given to the effects that inhomogeneity and instability will have on the participants performance
- **Sub-contractors - verification of PT samples:** - the PT provider must demonstrate that the subcontractors experience and technical competence are sufficient for their assigned tasks, for example, their test is accredited to ISO:17025 or a similar test type is accredited to the same, or other acclaimed attribute such as the laboratory is a recognised centre of excellence etc
- **Subcontractor – comments on PT scheme results:** - Referred to in this context as a 'Test Commentator' (TC) is someone whose field of expertise is used when providing an evaluation of the participants results and test procedures to support and provide advice on testing practices
- **Operation of scheme:** - Determine how samples (including data/images etc) are to be handled, stored, and distributed for example FTP platform, email, by courier in compliance with International Air Transport Association (IATA regs) temperature dependencies, whether participants require import permits etc.
- **Documentation:** - Detail the selection of measurand(s) or characteristic(s) of interest including what is to be identified, measured, or tested and design/produce relevant documentation.
- **Participation:** - This details the pilot scheme
- **Distribution:** - Determine frequency of PT/EQA/RT, issue dates and time limits for participants from receipt, testing and submitting results
- **Results reporting:** - formatting of the report, what it should contain and how data will be displayed for example, assigned values, criteria for pass/fail, any statistical analysis, performance evaluation techniques and when report will be published
- **Costing:** - Determine cost of running PT for example, Full economic cost (FEC) and any commercial

This task is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP.
This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

- **Procedures:** - Standard operating procedures (local or otherwise) any cross reference to statutory requirements or reference methods
- **Validation/Verification of pilot exercise:** - Does the pilot scheme meet participants requirements, seek, and record participants feedback and where necessary take action
- **Scheme- Fit for purpose:** - Does the scheme meet the required needs
- **Contracts:** - Will the scheme be provided to commercial customers
- **Resources:** can deliverables be met? Availability of material for PT/EQA/RT sample production, Staff, equipment etc
- **Sign off for approval to go live i.e., we can meet demand**

Appendix 3

Pilot PT on isolation/detection and characterization of pathogens

NEW PT SCHEME – PLANNING AND DESIGN

SCHEME PLAN

Scheme Title:	EJP CARE 'Pilot on typing/characterization including WGS'	PT Scheme number	2022
Introduction and purpose of scheme	<p>This proficiency test is provided to facilitate harmonization and standardization in whole genome sequencing and data analysis of single end and paired end sequencing, with the aim to produce comparable data for monitoring and research purposes.</p> <p>The PT consists of two parts and includes assessing (1a) the laboratory's DNA preparation and sequencing procedures and (1b) the laboratory's sequencing output.</p> <p>The PT focuses on <i>Escherichia coli</i>, <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>, and <i>Enterococcus faecium/faecalis</i>, and allows for sign-up for each species separately. Note that item 1a and item 1b are parallel; <i>i.e.</i> when signing up for 1a for one species, participation in 1b is expected.</p> <p>The two items consist of</p> <p>1a) DNA extraction, purification, library-preparation, and whole-genome-sequencing of six bacterial cultures; two <i>Escherichia coli</i> strains, two <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> strains, and two <i>Enterococcus faecium/faecalis</i> strains. Participants will be requested to submit reads using ScienceData and to identify the Multi Locus Sequence Type (MLST) of the strains, and the antimicrobial resistance genes present in the strains if the laboratory performs this type of analysis routinely.</p> <p>1b) Perform whole-genome-sequencing of pre-prepared DNA (each vial contains a minimum of 2 µg DNA) delivered by the PT organisers of the same six bacterial strains mentioned in clause 1a. For clause 1b, participants will also be requested to submit reads using ScienceData and to identify the Multi Locus Sequence Type (MLST) of the strains, and the antimicrobial resistance genes present in the strains if the laboratory performs this type of analysis routinely.</p>		
What are the challenges for participants, other than finding the target analyte, does the scheme offer? e.g. dilutions of the same sample, duplicate samples, negatives, sera with antibodies to other diseases	Participants receive two types of samples, one is the pure bacterial cultures and for this, purification of DNA must be done prior to sequencing and data analysis.		
Determinands:	Pure cultures of bacteria isolates and dried, purified DNA of the same bacteria isolates		
Test method(s):	Culturing, purification of DNA, whole genome sequencing and bioinformatics analysis	Sample type (in final form)	<p>Swabs of live bacterial cultures, dried purified DNA of the same bacterial cultures</p> <p>The Salmonella and E. coli strains are shipped as swabs (Amies agar gel with charcoal; Copan Transystem™) whereas the Campylobacter strains are shipped as charcoal swabs (Stuarts Transportmedium).</p> <p>The pre-prepared DNA is sent as dried samples.</p>

NEW PT SCHEME – PLANNING AND DESIGN

TECHNICAL EXPERTS CONSULTED

<p>Technical expert involved at scheme planning (name) – test / disease expert, statistician, other. Give reason for using this expert.</p>	<p>Comments / advice given: A bioinformatician and a microbiologist in collaboration agree on the setup of the scheme and contribute to defining the expected results</p>
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WGS PTs STRAIN SELECTION

- Strain selection inclusive of different sectors e.g vet, human, food

SAMPLE DETAILS

Number of samples per distribution	6 live bacterial cultures and 6 samples of DNA corresponding to the included bacterial cultures.
Sample volume	
Where raw material is obtained, what is the source / origin	DTU Food strain collection
Samples produced In-house or external provider	In-house
Details of how samples are produced:	<p>Bacterial cultures are subcultured and pure, live cultures are transferred to swabs in a relevant transport or growth medium. From the same bacterial cultures, DNA is purified and aliquoted into vials after which it is dried and ready for shipment.</p>
Primary test method used to verify the sample / bulk stock / product	DNA from the bacterial cultures is sequenced after which it undergoes bioinformatic analysis based on the components included in the PT.
Details of how/where samples are dispatched from. If dispatched externally, how has the dispatcher been assessed and deemed acceptable	Samples are dispatched from DTU Food (the provider institution).
Where samples/material have been subjected to any inactivation procedure how is it known that this has not ruined the product	Not applicable
Where appropriate have the samples / material been checked to ensure the disease causing agent is non viable? Is the inactivation process validated?	Not applicable
<p>Homogeneity (section 4.4.3 ISO/IEC 17043) Method used to ensure homogeneity (where applicable) Criteria used to define acceptability of the test results for homogeneity eg no of samples tested that should all give the sample interpretation of the result – or where enumeration is used is there a range of where the results should lie. Give details of Method used to ensure homogeneity where applicable</p> <p>What effect would non – homogeneous samples or batch of samples have on the intended result or the participants results</p>	<p>Homogeneity of the of the swabs of live bacterial cultures consist in that they are pure and live. This is ensured during the production of the swabs by the described procedure for production of the swabs and by subsequently confirming the expected results when subjecting the purity control to each of the components of the PT.</p> <p>Homogeneity of the DNA consist in producing DNA in one pool and confirming the expected results when subjecting the and aliquot of the DNA to each of the components of the PT.</p>
<p>Stability (section 4.4.3 ISO/IEC 17043) Expiry of samples or shelf life applied. How stability has been assessed.</p>	Stability of the swabs of live bacterial cultures are setup all through the period from shipment till deadline of submission of results.

NEW PT SCHEME – PLANNING AND DESIGN

Consider how instability would affect participants results	
Record metrological traceability of samples: e.g. reference strains (may not always be possible for all samples)	Not applicable
Criteria used to define acceptability of intended result	Antimicrobial Resistance Gene detected Chromosomal mutation detected Phenotypic antimicrobial resistance correctly predicted MLST correct Serotype correct
Information to be included on intended result for final report	Information includes method details as well as obtained results
Is sample availability limited e.g scarce	Yes
Any potential major sources of error	None detected
Establish the criteria for uncertainty	

	Handling requirements	Storage requirements
Raw material	As described in DTU Food SOP's	Bacterial cultures: Refrigerator
Samples in final form	As described in DTU Food SOP's	Bacterial cultures: Refrigerator Dried DNA: Room temperature
On receipt by lab	<p>In the PT protocol, participants are guided to:</p> <p>Subculture the bacterial strains on a growth medium relevant for the organism in question and incubate. Following incubation and assessment of purity of the bacterial cultures, perform DNA extraction and WGS according to the laboratory's standard procedure.</p> <p>For the pre-prepared DNA received, perform WGS according to the laboratory's standard procedure.</p> <p>While handling both bacterial cultures and pre-prepared DNA (items 1a and 1b), register relevant information. For this purpose, Appendix 3 (testforms) gives an overview of the requested data (information and results) relevant to the sequencing and the analysis of the sequences, whereas Appendix 2 (manual for the webtool) presents the information on how to access the webtool and the procedure for submission of data.</p>	<p>In the PT protocol, participants are guided to:</p> <p>Upon receipt, store the swab cultures (bacterial cultures) at 5-25°C until microbial analysis. We suggest that you sub-culture and prepare the cultures for storage in your strain collection (e.g. in a -80°C freezer) within 48 hours from reception of the parcel.</p> <p>You will receive the pre-prepared DNA as dried samples. Upon receipt, either rehydrate your sample (please see further details under 3.3.2 Item 1b; DNA) and store the <u>liquid dried</u> samples at room temperature in closed tubes to prevent evaporation, or store the samples in</p> <p>(a) A dry storage cabinet at room temperature (15-25°C), or (b) A heat-sealed, moisture-barrier bag along with a silica gel desiccant pack, or (c) If sequencing of the samples is planned within the first 10 days of arrival of the shipment, you may store the dried samples in the zip-lock bag in which they arrived along with the silica gel desiccant pack. If moisture starts to appear, the desiccant pack must be changed.</p>
Details of Safety aspects issued (to be completed by sample production department):	As described in DTU Food SOP's	

NEW PT SCHEME – PLANNING AND DESIGN

SUPPLIERS OF MATERIAL & SAMPLES

Source for supply of samples or material for samples (name, location & details) YES / NO	Selection of strains was based on the suggested strains by EJP CARE partners who contributed with strains for this purpose	
Give details of samples/material supplier's status ie quality status or other reason they are approved as a supplier Incl details for both positive and negative samples.	Cultures were tested and confirmed at DTU Food prior to including them as test strains.	

WGS DATA COLLECTION

Which platforms were used for the analysis of the WGS sequences	Antimicrobial genes and mutations were detected using ResFinder v4.1, using default parameters (90% identity, 60% coverage) and were subsequently manually curated. Sequence types (MLST) were found with the cge tool MLST v2.0. E. coli serotypes were determined with SeroTypefinder v2.0. S. enterica they were obtained with SeqSero 1.2. Species were verified using kmerfinder v3.2.
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SUB CONTRACTORS - TESTING OF SAMPLES

	Test 1	Test 2	Test 3
Record test method(s) details	Detection of Antimicrobial Resistance Gene Detection of Chromosomal mutation Prediction of phenotypic antimicrobial resistance Determination of MLST Determination of serotype		
Lab(s) used for checking / validation of samples or raw material (name, location & details)	WBVR, Netherlands		
Are they ISO17025 accredited for the relevant test	No		
Are they ISO17025 accredited other similar test but not the relevant test	For WGS, no accreditation is in place, though for a number of other methods, accreditation according to ISO 17025 is in place No		
Are they certified to ISO 9001	No		
Do they hold a status of national/ international ref centre or known centre of excellence/quality	Yes		
Are they a long term subcontractor/collaborator for DTU Food with a proven track record	Yes		
Do they meet other defined requirements eg specialist facilities	Yes		
Details of any other assessment or evaluation of testing sub-contractor	None		
where applicable record the Consensus values – where used indicate why and estimate the uncertainty of the assigned value	Captured in separate overview		

NEW PT SCHEME – PLANNING AND DESIGN

Environmental conditions (section 4.3 ISO/IEC 17043) Give consideration to storage, transportation and subcontractors facilities. Include handling and disposal of hazardous materials.	Sample handling covered by the subcontractor's ISO17025 accreditation		
Equipment. Suitability and monitoring: State if covered by ISO 17025. If not assess alternative quality system suitability eg – validated method used or are SOP's / protocols implemented or manufacturers instructions used. Are calibration certificates held? Use of reference stds. Note if QC or PT samples are used to check equipment suitability, and confirm method reliability / method validation	Equipment covered by the subcontractor's quality assurance system		
Other comments	Not applicable		

SUBCONTRACTOR – SCHEME COMMENTS

Name and location of Primary, deputy, secondary test commentators (TC) (for provision of evaluation of results)	Primary TC: Mike Brouwer, WBVR, the Netherlands Secondary TC: Kees Veldman, WBVR, the Netherlands
Rationale for selection of TC(s)	Mike Brouwer is Senior Researcher Antibiotic resistance (with competence within the field of bioinformatics) Kees Veldman is Head of National Reference Laboratory on Antimicrobial Resistance in animals (microbiologist)
CV / details of experience	Mike Brouwer has expertise within: Bacteriology, Microbiology, Molecular biology, Molecular genetics, Bacteria, Antibiotic resistance, Escherichia coli, DNA sequencing, Next generation sequencing Kees Veldman has expertise within: Bacteriology, Molecular biology, Antibiotic resistance
Have TC's been sent confidentiality agreement, guidelines for TC's and details of what appears on the TC report, compared to the final report issued to participants.	No

OPERATION OF SCHEME

Sample distribution - postage requirements	IATA packaging – UN3373
Additional requirements;	None
Samples to be issued by (eg DTU Food or other dept)	PT Coordinator

DOCUMENTATION / PT LIMS

Standard paperwork for labwork file		
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NEW PT SCHEME – PLANNING AND DESIGN

Sample request sheet (standard template which may need amending depending on sample type and tests done).	Not applicable
Stock list produced	Not applicable
Scheme details entered on computer	Not applicable
Scheme details	Documented
Sample No. sequence	Not applicable
Test information – test type, result & method items	Documented
Scheme instructions for labs – ensure these do not impinge on a labs routine method. Has storage upon receipt been included	Documented
Results tabulation- Results reporting form agreed (Note: no DANAK symbol to be applied initially until PT is awarded accreditation)	Yes

PARTICIPATION

Pilot scheme due	October 2021
Likely Number of participants in pilot	15
Participant criteria to be met before joining scheme (where applicable)	Partner in EJP CARE
Collusion – consider the potential for collusion (incl post distribution to pre disclosure of results and any preventative measures)	Expected results are not available until after deadline.

DISTRIBUTION

Fixed Term? YES /NO (if yes enter period)	YES / NO 26 October 2021
Time limit from distribution to deadline for results	8 weeks
Week of issue	1
Frequency of issue (e.g. monthly or state months)	Once

RESULTS REPORTING

Assigned values/intended results – how displayed	Expected results displayed on individual evaluation report: Antimicrobial Resistance Gene Chromosomal mutation Predicted phenotypic antimicrobial resistance MLST serotype
Data reported to participants as (eg electronic tabulated results showing all participants results)	Electronic – presents all the participants obtained results and the PT provider's expected results
How performance evaluation techniques are assessed/displayed where appropriate (eg mean of sample results)	Not applicable
Specific requirements on results reporting to be agreed externally?	Not applicable
Statistical analysis carried out – yes / no (if yes, by whom)	No
Basis of performance evaluation techniques	Correct results submitted in accordance with ResFinder, MLST finder, SeroTypeFinder and SeqSero
Details of result / report to be published	November 2022

COSTING

Costing record (filename) Full economic cost (FEC)	Not applicable
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NEW PT SCHEME – PLANNING AND DESIGN

Costing carried out by	Not applicable
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PROCEDURES

	Sample production	Scheme operation
Nominated author (if in-house)		
SOP number		
SOP title		
Related National SOP reference(s) for test method if known e.g. ISO	Not applicable	

VALIDATION (PT fit for purpose) / VERIFICATION (meets participants requirements)

Pilot Scheme

Distribution Number	2021
Date of issue	Not applicable
Participants as distribution list?	Yes
Further pilots required yes / no if yes give details	No
Has the feedback form been sent to participants following pilot scheme.	No
Did all participants' results match the intended results?	No Data has been validated and apart from individual evaluation reports for each participating laboratory, an overall report has been issued
Were the samples used at an appropriate dilution in terms of the test and for economic reasons (ie. so no wastage of material)	Yes
Is there any further action to be taken?	No

SCHEME – FIT FOR PURPOSE

What criteria is used to determine the scheme is fit for purpose	Criteria developed for the purpose of this pilot PT and discussed in the PT report.
Does the scheme meet the proposed requirements ?	Yes
Signature / Date (Head or Deputy Head of Unit)	

CONTRACTS

Is scheme now to be offered commercially? Give date if yes	No
Contracts – Type of contracts for non APHA labs e.g. using routine commercial contracts or using a project code	Not applicable
Has a PT scheme information sheet been finalised and published on website? Has the PT been added to the price list?	Not applicable
Signature / Date	Not applicable

OTHER INFORMATION / COMMENTS RELEVANT TO SCHEME

The EJP CARE 'Pilot on typing/characterization including WGS' was successful in allowing for obtaining an indication of the EJP CARE partners' ability to perform sequencing and perform bioinformatic analysis of the sequences in relation to the antimicrobial resistance and typing based on MLST and serotype of the test material.

NEW PT SCHEME – PLANNING AND DESIGN

RESOURCES

Contract Review - Deliverables established

Criteria	Available	Criteria	Available	
Staff	Appropriate number	<input type="checkbox"/>	Training	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Provision for staff turnover	<input type="checkbox"/>	Experience	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Sufficient supervisors/management	<input type="checkbox"/>	Competence	<input type="checkbox"/>
Lab accommodation	Adequate space	<input type="checkbox"/>	Adequate storage for samples	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Adequate heating / ventilation	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Consumables / materials	Suppliers approved	<input type="checkbox"/>	Quantities assessed / deliverable	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Sufficient PT material	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Safety	Risk assessed	<input type="checkbox"/>	Samples	<input type="checkbox"/>
Equipment / IT	All necessary equipment available	<input type="checkbox"/>	Data processing software	<input type="checkbox"/>
		Yes		No
Sufficient resources for PT Scheme		<input type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>
Signed	Name		Date	

Appendix 4

Pilot PT on outbreak surveillance based on WGS data

NEW PT SCHEME – PLANNING AND DESIGN

SCHEME PLAN

Scheme Title:	PT on outbreak surveillance based on WGS data	PT Scheme number	Care Pilot-study
Introduction and purpose of scheme	<p>The purpose of this scheme, which is a pilot PT, is to evaluate the participant's ability to identify clusters of closely related organism of foodborne pathogenic bacteria, when using their routine methods for cluster detection.</p> <p>The pilot scheme is conducted as part of the One-Health-EJP programme CARE, and the PT participants are all member of the CARE consortium or otherwise selected as eligible for participation in the PT. The participants represents both the human health sector and food and veterinary sectors, and the participants are all functioning as National Reference Laboratories or actively involved in the surveillance of foodborne human disease.</p> <p>The experiences from this pilot scheme will be used to develop guidelines on how to perform similar cluster detection PTs in the future.</p> <p>Cross-sectorial exchange of WGS based typing data are essential for the identification of potential foodborne sources of outbreaks and an important purpose of the scheme is to evaluate the cross-sectorial performance of WGS based typing. The scheme evaluates the ability to identify clusters among three pathogens, Salmonella Campylobacter and Listeria monocytogens.</p> <p>The basis for the scheme is samples in the form of FASTQ files, that represents raw reads of DNA extracted from pure cultures of the target pathogens. The participants will get access to FASTQ files from three different distributions of the selected pathogens. The FASTQ files are generated from real-life isolates that have been anonymized in compliance with the European General Data Protection Regulation, GDPR.</p> <p>The participants shall analyze the FASTQ files with their current operational pipelines for WGS based cluster detection. The laboratories shall use their routine quality control (QC), and only include samples that passed QC for further analysis For all samples, the sequence type (ST) shall be reported, and it should be indicated whether the sample was a part of a closely related cluster. For Salmonella or Campylobacter, the serovar or the species should also be reported. Both allele and/or SNP based cluster analytical approaches can be used. The reporting of results includes general questions on the cluster analysis approach, including information on the applied bioinformatics tools for each of the three pathogens. Additionally the participants are asked to report the number of allele and or SNP distances using selected index samples as references.</p>		
What are the challenges for participants, other than finding the target analyte, does the scheme offer? e.g. dilutions of the same sample, duplicate samples, negatives, sera with antibodies to other diseases	The main goal for the participants is to define the samples that clusters in the three distributions.		
Determinands:			
Test method(s):	Freedom of choice – the participants should use their current operational pipelines..	Sample type (in final form)	DNA sequences in FASTQ format

TECHNICAL EXPERTS CONSULTED

Technical expert involved at scheme planning (name) – test / disease expert, statistician, other. Give reason for using this expert.	<p>Comments / advice given:</p> <p>CARE network have been included in the planning phase. Qualified persons from SSI and AHPA have been responsible for the execution. The results of the scheme will be discussed with the participants – that are also experts.</p>

WGS PTs STRAIN SELECTION

NEW PT SCHEME – PLANNING AND DESIGN

SAMPLE DETAILS

Number of samples per distribution	The PT includes WGS data from three distributions of 35, 27 and 31 samples of <i>Campylobacter</i> , <i>L. monocytogenes</i> , and <i>Salmonella</i> , respectively.
Sample volume	NA
Where raw material is obtained, what is the source / origin	The three distributions (FASTQ files) includes clustering samples (human outbreaks) and sporadic background samples. The samples are from the strain collection of SSI. The samples are anonymised in compliance with the EU General Data Protection Regulation.
Samples produced In-house or external provider	The samples were selected/produced by SSI
Details of how samples are produced:	The samples represents FASTQ files that had passed the standard quality assurance pipeline applied at SSI
Primary test method used to verify the sample / bulk stock / product	After anonymisation the samples were tested using the SSI standard operational set up.
Details of how/where samples are dispatched from. If dispatched externally, how has the dispatcher been assessed and deemed acceptable	The distributions will be shared on a FTP site hosted by SSI: All participants will receive unique log on informations to the FTP share site. The site will be organized in three folders, one for each of the pathogens. Each folder will contains the FASTQ files and instructions for the participants for how to perform the analysis.
Where samples/material have been subjected to any inactivation procedure how is it known that this has not ruined the product	NA
Where appropriate have the samples / material been checked to ensure the disease causing agent is non viable? Is the inactivation process validated?	NA
Homogeneity (section 4.4.3 ISO/IEC 17043) Method used to ensure homogeneity (where applicable) Criteria used to define acceptability of the test results for homogeneity eg no of samples tested that should all give the sample interpretation of the result – or where enumeration is used is there a range of where the results should lie. Give details of Method used to ensure homogeneity where applicable What effect would non – homogeneous samples or batch of samples have on the intended result or the participants results	The participants will receive the same samples – DNA data in FASTQ format.
Stability (section 4.4.3 ISO/IEC 17043) Expiry of samples or shelf life applied. How stability has been assessed. Consider how instability would affect participants results	NA
Record metrological traceability of samples: e.g. reference strains (may not always be possible for all samples)	Traceability of the samples back to the patient/source is not possible due to GDPR, but the DNA sequences can be traced back to the FTP share site, and the isolates have been saved at SSI and deposited to the CARE collection of reference material. .
Criteria used to define acceptability of intended result	The main focus will be to evaluate the participants are ability to identify the , ST, species/serotype and clusters.
Information to be included on intended result for final report	The results will be evaluated and compared with the results of the PT provider as well as all reported results. In the case of deviating results it will be analysed whether there exists explanations for the deviations, as different methodologies and cluster definitions are in use in different institutions.
Is sample availability limited e.g scarce	NA
Any potential major sources of error	T
Establish the criteria for uncertainty	

NEW PT SCHEME – PLANNING AND DESIGN

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	Handling requirements	Storage requirements
Raw material	NA	Disk storage space
Samples in final form	FASTQ file format	
On receipt by lab	Files to be downloaded by participating labs	
Details of Safety aspects issued (to be completed by sample production department):		NA

SUPPLIERS OF MATERIAL & SAMPLES

Source for supply of samples or material for samples (name, location & details) YES / NO	NA	
Give details of samples/material supplier's status ie quality status or other reason they are approved as a supplier Incl details for both positive and negative samples.	The supplier of the samples is accredited according to ISO 17025, but the analytical set up for cluster detection is not accredited.	

WGS DATA COLLECTION

- Platforms used
- Cluster detection

SUB CONTRACTORS - TESTING OF SAMPLES

	Test 1	Test 2	Test 3
Record test method(s) details			
Lab(s) used for checking / validation of samples or raw material (name, location & details)	SSI		
Are they ISO17025 accredited for the relevant test	No, but SSI are accredited to perform other analysis under the ISO17025 accreditation.		
Are they ISO17025 accredited other similar test but not the relevant test	NA		
Are they certified to ISO 9001	NA		
Do they hold a status of national/ international ref centre or known centre of excellence/quality	The participating institutions are all serving as reference laboratories or performing national surveillance in their countries		
Are they a long term subcontractor for VETQAS with a proven track record	No		
Do they meets other defined requirements eg specialist facilities	YES? What are the requirements		
Details of any other assessment or evaluation of testing sub-contractor	NA		
where applicable record the Consensus values – where used indicate why and estimate the	NA		

NEW PT SCHEME – PLANNING AND DESIGN

uncertainty of the assigned value			
Environmental conditions (section 4.3 ISO/IEC 17043) Give consideration to storage, transportation and subcontractors facilities. If the subcontractor is part of APHA group, has this been assessed under their ISO17025 audit? Include handling and disposal of hazardous materials.	NA		
Equipment. Suitability and monitoring: State if covered by ISO 17025. If not assess alternative quality system suitability eg – validated method used or are SOP's / protocols implemented or manufacturers instructions used. Are calibration certificates held? Use of reference stds, Note if QC or PT samples are used to check equipment suitability, and confirm method reliability / method validation	NA		
Other comments			

SUBCONTRACTOR – SCHEME COMMENTS

Name and location of Primary, deputy, secondary test commentators (TC) (for provision of evaluation of results)	Mia, Jeppe and other staff members at SSI Paula, Sally, Nick, APHA The CARE network
Rationale for selection of TC(s)	The TCs have all hands on experience with WGS based cluster detection
CV / details of experience	NA
Have TC's been sent confidentiality agreement, guidelines for TC's and details of what appears on the TC report, compared to the final report issued to participants.	NO

OPERATION OF SCHEME

Sample distribution - postage requirements	None
Additional requirements;	None
Samples to be issued by (eg VETQAS or other dept)	None

DOCUMENTATION / PT LIMS

Standard paperwork for labwork file	
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NEW PT SCHEME – PLANNING AND DESIGN

Sample request sheet (standard template which may need amending depending on sample type and tests done).	The participants are expected to store the raw data of their analysis.
Stock list produced	?
Scheme details entered on computer	?
Scheme details	Provided via meetings with the participants and instructions for the execution of the analysis and reporting of the results to the APHA platform
Sample No. sequence	Se above
Test information – test type, result & method items	Se above
Scheme instructions for labs – ensure these do not impinge on a labs routine method. Has storage upon receipt been included	Instructions for uploading results sent to the participants using the standard APHA platform, which were further developed to accommodate the reporting of this PT. The results will be consolidated on the APHA platform and exported to an excel spreadsheet, where the data analysis have been conducted.
Results tabulation- Results reporting form agreed (Note: no UKAS symbol to be applied initially until PT is awarded accreditation)	?

PARTICIPATION

Pilot scheme due	December 2021
Likely Number of participants in pilot	12-15
Participant criteria to be met before joining scheme (where applicable)	Member of the CARE consortium or approved as an eligible laboratory by the CARE consortium.
Collusion – consider the potential for collusion (incl post distribution to pre disclosure of results and any preventative measures)	The participants download the same samples and the samples have the same numbers in all laboratories. Therefore collusion is possible. However, the laboratories participates voluntarily, and in most cases the reported results need to be substantiated with data that justifies the submitted results.

DISTRIBUTION

Fixed Term? YES /NO (if yes enter period)	YES, distribution available on December 15. 2021
Time limit from distribution to deadline for results	Yes, deadline set by the end of February 2022
Week of issue	
Frequency of issue (e.g. monthly or state months)	

RESULTS REPORTING

Assigned values/intended results – how displayed	Results to be reported on a specially developed platform based on the standard APHA platform.
Data reported to participants as (eg electronic tabulated results showing all participants results)	Each laboratory will receive an individual evaluation of their submitted results compared to the PT provider. All results of the PT will be made available in a report, where the participants are pseudo-anonymized, meaning that each participant can identify their own results and compare these with results from other participants. .
How performance evaluation techniques are assessed/displayed where appropriate (eg mean of sample results)	NA
Specific requirements on results reporting to be agreed externally?	NA
Statistical analysis carried out – yes / no (if yes, by whom)	NO
Basis of performance evaluation techniques	Discussions with the CARE participants at meetings before and after the PT is executed
Details of result / report to be published	A final report of the PT will be circulated among the participants and published on the EJP-CARE website.

NEW PT SCHEME – PLANNING AND DESIGN

COSTING

Costing record (filename) Full economic cost (FEC)	NA
Costing carried out by	NA

PROCEDURES

	Sample production	Scheme operation	
Nominated author (if in-house)			
SOP number			
SOP title			
Related National SOP reference(s) for test method if known e.g. ISO			

VALIDATION (PT fit for purpose) / VERIFICATION (meets participants requirements)

Pilot Scheme

Distribution Number	NA
Date of issue	
Participants as distribution list?	The participating will be formally invited by an e-mail with a like where they can indicate the name of their institute, etc. The participants shall report a responsible persons that will be responsible for all contact, reporting, etc, that relates to the PT
Further pilots required yes / no if yes give details	Perhaps
Has the feedback form been sent to participants following pilot scheme.	Yes
Did all participants' results match the intended results?	Overall, yes
Were the samples used at an appropriate dilution in terms of the test and for economic reasons (ie. so no wastage of material)	NA
Is there any further action to be taken?	The overall PT report should be finalized and discussed with the participants

SCHEME – FIT FOR PURPOSE

What criteria is used to determine the scheme is fit for purpose	The participants should be able to call ST, speces/serotype and define the clusters that are defined by the PT provider for each of the three distributions.
Does the scheme meet the proposed requirements ?	Yes
Signature / Date (Head or Deputy Head of Unit)	

CONTRACTS

Is scheme now to be offered commercially? Give date if yes	NA
Contracts – Type of contracts for non APHA labs e.g. using routine commercial contracts or using a project code	NA
Has a PT scheme information sheet been finalised and published on website? Has the PT been added to the price list?	NA
Signature / Date	

OTHER INFORMATION / COMMENTS RELEVANT TO SCHEME

NEW PT SCHEME – PLANNING AND DESIGN

RESOURCES

Contract Review - Deliverables established

Criteria	Available	Criteria	Available	
Staff	Appropriate number	<input type="checkbox"/>	Training	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Provision for staff turnover	<input type="checkbox"/>	Experience	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Sufficient supervisors/management	<input type="checkbox"/>	Competence	<input type="checkbox"/>
Lab accommodation	Adequate space	<input type="checkbox"/>	Adequate storage for samples	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Adequate heating / ventilation	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Consumables / materials	Suppliers approved	<input type="checkbox"/>	Quantities assessed / deliverable	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Sufficient PT material	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Safety	Risk assessed	<input type="checkbox"/>	Samples	<input type="checkbox"/>
Equipment / IT	All necessary equipment available	<input type="checkbox"/>	Data processing software	<input type="checkbox"/>
Sufficient resources for PT Scheme	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>		No <input type="checkbox"/>	
Signed	Name		Date	